

RESEARCH REPORT
May, 2024
TREPA Series 22-2024

Training Guide for Data Enumerators

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TREPA

Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People, and Animals

TREPA PUBLICATION SERIES

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CITE THIS DOCUMENT:

Baule, S. *Training Guide for Data Enumerators*. Threat Reduction for the Environment, People and Animals. Department of Geographical Sciences, College of Behavioral and Social Sciences, University of Maryland, College Park. College Park, MD. 18 pp.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We extend our sincere gratitude to the collaborators from the communities surrounding the Great Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area (GLTFCA) and beyond for their invaluable contributions to this study. We are particularly indebted to the Limpopo National Park and its staff, especially Mr. Tomas Meque Chauque, for their unwavering support throughout this research phase. Our appreciation also extends to community leaders who facilitated the recruitment process of the data enumerators. Additionally, we would like to acknowledge the significant contributions of our other collaborators, including Félix Marecha, whose insights were instrumental in refining our research guidelines and tools. Their collective expertise and dedication have been crucial to the success of this phase of study.

The Threat Reduction for the Environment, People, and Animals (TREPA) research project has obtained research clearances in all involved jurisdictions (South Africa, Mozambique, and the United States). TREPA's research methods have been reviewed and granted approval by (i) the Institutional Review Boards of the University of Maryland, College Park, University of Texas Austin, University of Alabama, and Colorado State University, (ii) Universidade de Licungo, (iii) Witwatersrand University's Human Research Ethics Committee (non-medical) H24/03/10, (iv) University of Cape Town LAW/00673/2024 and LAW/01056/2024, (v) the Office of Human Research Oversight OHRO Log Number E05089 and Log Number E05089.1c, and (vi) the Administração Nacional das Áreas de Conservação research permit No. 1/11/2023 valid from November 6, 2023 to November 6, 2024.

The project or effort depicted was or is sponsored by the Department of Defense, Defense Threat Reduction Agency. The content of the information does not necessarily reflect the position or the policy of the federal government, and no official endorsement should be inferred.

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INTRODUCTION

This document served as a training manual for data enumerators who participated in human subjects' data collection activities related to community-based and participatory research. The research focused on building knowledge mitigating security risks stemming from the intersectionality of wildlife trafficking and biosafety concerns related to zoonotic pathogens in the Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area (GLTFCA) in Africa.

Comprehensive training sessions aimed to ensure that data enumerators were thoroughly familiar with standardized research procedures and proficient in using the required tools. To maintain consistency and reliability of data collection, all enumerators were instructed to adhere to standardized interviewing criteria when engaging with participants. Prior to field deployment, and to verify that data enumerators had been sufficiently acquainted with the data collection procedures, data enumerators underwent a pre-test evaluation. This assessment served a dual purpose: it allowed researchers to identify areas for improvement in the research tools and simultaneously prepared enumerators for field conditions. This rigorous preparation process aimed to enhance the quality and consistency of data collection throughout the study.

TRAINING SESSIONS

The research team secured essential resources to facilitate comprehensive training for data enumerators. A suitable venue was procured, meeting the following criteria: indoor location, adequate lighting, comfortable environment, and appropriate furnishings, including tables, chairs, writing boards, and access to power outlets. The team also provided all necessary training materials, which included:

- a) Visual aids: Tripod and flip charts;
- b) Writing implements: Pens, pencils, and markers;
- c) Documentation tools: Notebooks;
- d) Recording equipment: Digital audio recorders, memory cards, and USB drives.

This meticulous preparation ensured that enumerators had access to all required resources, thereby optimizing the effectiveness of the training process and, by extension, the quality of subsequent data collection.

I. Training

The training sessions reviewed the data collection tools in order:

- a) Structured interviews
- b) Participatory risk mapping
- c) Grazing mapping
- d) Focus group
- e) Social network analysis tools

II. Pilot Study

To ensure proficiency and consistency in data collection, each enumerator had to conduct pilot interviews with two individuals. This pre-testing phase served multiple purposes: i) Assessing the effectiveness and clarity of the data collection instruments; ii) allowing enumerators to apply their training in a realistic setting; iii) familiarizing enumerators with both paper-based and digital

recording methods and iv) confirming that all enumerators have a uniform understanding of key concepts and methodologies.

III. Tools and Sample Size

Structured interviews

The target sample size for the structured interviews was 20 participants. Each enumerator was trained on how to identify and select research participants using a set of selection criteria including gender parity, current residency in the community, and age (18 years and above). Participants should be selected randomly by each data enumerator on the road, within the communities of the research setting.

There was 1 data collection team on the ground, which was comprised of 4 to 6 members: 2 to 3 TREPA researchers, 2 data enumerators, and park personnel (who was not directly involved in data collection). This team was expected to interview 20 research participants in total, in each community. Structured interviews were conducted in the communities designated as fieldwork sites and were expected to last for 1 day in each community.

Participatory risk mapping

The sample size for the participatory risk mapping was 20 participants. Each enumerator was trained on how to instruct and guide the research participants (10 men and 10 women of different age groups per community) in the mapping activity to identify on a map certain locations related to domestic livestock, wild animals, human-wildlife conflicts, conservation crime, and sickness of the environment, people, and animals. Each enumerator was assigned to a group of 20 participants: 10 men and 10 women that were preselected using a set of selection criteria including, knowing livestock, gender parity, current residency in the community, and age (18 years and above).

The data collection team was comprised of 4 to 5 members: 2 to 3 TREPA members and 2 data enumerators. This team was expected to oversee the participatory risk mapping, in each community, with minimum to no interference. Participatory risk mapping was conducted in the communities selected as field sites and it lasted for 2 and a half to 3 hours in each community.

Grazing mapping

The target sample size for the participatory risk mapping of livestock grazing in endemic anthrax zones was 16 participants per community. Each data enumerator was trained on how to instruct and guide the participants (selected families) in marking the areas where they graze their livestock. Each enumerator was assigned to a family that was preselected using a set of selection criteria, including having the most livestock or being recognized in the community as such, knowing livestock grazing, gender parity, current residency in the community, and age (18 years and above).

The composition of the participants was as follows: 1 senior female, 1 senior male, 1 young female over 18 and 1 young male over 18 per family. These were selected by a TREPA team member, within the communities that had been selected as field sites prior to the data collection activity. There was 1 participatory grazing mapping supervisory team which was comprised of 4 to 5 members: 2 to 3 TREPA members and 2 data enumerators. This team was expected to oversee the participatory risk mapping of livestock grazing activities, in each community, with minimum to no interference. Participatory risk mapping of livestock grazing in endemic anthrax zones was conducted in the Pafuri region in Mozambique, and lasted 3 to 4 hours in each community.

Focus group discussions

The target sample size for the focus groups was 6 to 12 participants per community. The TREPA representative conducted the focus group interviews with support from data enumerators who were trained on how to enumerate focus group discussions. The research

participants were preselected using a set of selection criteria: 1) currently living in the Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area; 2) had self-confirmed lived experience or expertise with the wildlife economy in the Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area; 3) had self-confirmed lived experience or expertise with livestock management and/or crop farming in the Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area; 4) is 18 years or older. These participants were previously selected by a TREPA team member, within the communities that had been selected as field sites before the data collection activity took place. The research team was comprised of 4 to 5 members: 2 to 3 TREPA members and 2 data enumerators. Focus group interviews were conducted in the communities selected as field sites, and they lasted for 2 to 3 hours in each community.

Training Session Protocol

This section outlines the procedure for training data enumerators and provides a specific script designed to help them acquaint themselves with the data collection process for all field data collection activities.

I. Greetings and welcome remarks

At this point, the researchers started the training with initial greetings and welcoming remarks, explaining the overall conditions of the data enumerators' role.

“Good morning, ladies and gentlemen. Welcome to our meeting and thank you for accepting our invitation and taking the time to attend.

Today, we are gathered here in the [insert community's name] community to provide training for your participation in a project aimed at reducing security risks associated with the intersectionality of wildlife trafficking and biosafety related to zoonotic pathogens in the Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area in Africa. Over the next three days, we will offer comprehensive training and guidelines to ensure your effective collaboration with us and the local community.

Please be aware that your efforts with the TREPA research team will be compensated at a rate of US\$40 per day. The first day's payment will be provided upfront, with the remaining days compensated at the conclusion of the data collection activities. Additionally, you will receive a certificate from the University of Maryland, College Park Department of Geographical Sciences upon completion of the data enumerator training, which will also certify the number of hours you have contributed to this project.

We look forward to working with you and appreciate your dedication to this important initiative.”

II. Reporting Structure

Then, the reporting structure was communicated, following the script.

“As a data enumerator, you will report directly to the supervisor, [insert name], who is a member of the TREPA team.”

III. Role of the supervisor

The supervisor was responsible for ensuring the proper implementation of fieldwork activities and maintaining the quality of the data collected. Supervisors oversaw two enumerators in each community and collaborated with the TREPA coordination team and park personnel to support fieldwork and data collection activities.

IV. Responsibilities of selected data enumerators

At this point, responsibilities were communicated to data enumerators, and they were explained that the activities they were involved in helped to support obtaining crucial information on the intersectionality of wildlife trafficking and biosafety related to zoonotic pathogens in the Greater Limpopo Transfrontier Conservation Area (GLTFCA). They were communicated that their responsibilities were as follows:

- a) Recruiting participants for interviews;
- b) Collecting data using a tablet;
- c) Supporting other data collection activities by translating instructions, sharing guidelines, and providing guidance to participants.

“For the structured interviews, you will move around the community, seeking individuals to interview on the street. Your task is to ask questions and record participants’ answers on a tablet using a specific software called KoBo Collect. It is essential to obtain complete and accurate responses and to record them precisely. The success of the interview depends on the respondents’ willingness to cooperate and the accuracy with which you capture their

answers. Therefore, it is your job to gather and record this information with politeness, patience, and skill.

For participatory risk mapping, you will receive training on how to instruct and guide research participants (10 men and 10 women of different age groups per community) in mapping activities. These activities will cover topics such as domestic livestock, wild animals, human-wildlife conflicts, conservation crime, and the health of the environment, people, and animals. You will be assigned to a group of 20 research participants: 10 men and 10 women preselected based on criteria including livestock knowledge, gender parity, current residency in the community, and age (18 years and above). The data collection team will consist of you and 2 to 3 TREPA members, and you are expected to oversee the participatory risk mapping in each community with minimal interference.

For participatory grazing mapping, you will be trained to instruct and guide research participants (selected families) in marking the areas where they graze their livestock. You will be assigned to a family preselected based on criteria such as having the most livestock or being recognized in the community for this, livestock grazing knowledge, gender parity, current residency in the community, and age (18 years and above). You are expected to oversee the participatory mapping of livestock grazing activities in each community with minimal interference.

For focus group discussions, one of the TREPA representatives will conduct the focus group interviews with your support after you have been trained in conducting focus group interviews. The research team will consist of 4 to 5 members: 2 to 3 TREPA members and you, the data enumerators. The participants will include 3 senior females, 3 senior males, 3 young females over 18, and 3 young males over 18 per community.

The information you obtain is confidential. You are not allowed to discuss, gossip about, or show your records to anyone not employed on the TREPA project. Questionnaires should never be left unattended where unauthorized people may have access to them.”

V. Reasons for dismissal

Data enumerators were informed about the reasons for dismissal, by indicating that immediate dismissal would take place on any of the following grounds:

- a) The enumerator was found cheating, for example making up data and filling in the interview data without actually interviewing the respondent;
- b) The quality of his/her work did not meet Quality Assurance standards;
- c) If an enumerator turned up for work drunk or under the influence of any drugs;
- d) Insubordination: if the enumerator failed to heed instructions;
- e) Abusive or inappropriate behavior to respondents or other enumerators, in breach of basic TREPA conduct; and,
- f) Any illegal activities

VI. Politeness and respect for interviewees

Field teams were expected to meet or exceed three sets of standards:

- a) Data quality assurance standards (Quality is defined as follows: completely filled out and legible answers);
- b) Accountability standards (human and material resources);
- c) Standards of conduct

The following script was communicated to the data enumerators:

“Data enumeration is a tiring and often stressful process. Enumerators can become frustrated and need to relax. TREPA expects the highest standards of conduct at all times. It goes without saying that you must respect the law, and we will not protect you if you fail to do so. But we expect more. It is extremely important for the TREPA staff to be courteous with the respondents and any other officials/individuals they encounter in the field. More

importantly, you should at all times put up a neutral appearance, in other words, respondents should perceive you as people who are likely to understand and accept them and what they have to say. You must be seen as people to whom respondents' reactions/views will not sound foreign or offensive. Courteousness and unbiased reactions during the interviews will generate the most accurate information from respondents."

VII. Cultural sensitivity

At this point, researchers discussed cultural sensitivities by following the script below:

"Given that our research spans a wide range of cultures and religions, it is crucial for you to remain impartial in your views and respect all cultures. Your personal beliefs should not influence the interviews in any way. Additionally, you must always adhere to local customs. For example, if a female interviewer is expected to wear a veil in an area with Muslim influence or a Capulana within the local community to respect local tradition, these customs should be followed."

VIII. Confidentiality

Confidentiality discussions ensued, following the script below:

"Participant anonymity is a fundamental principle of research, crucial for reassuring the public and increasing their willingness to participate in interviews. This anonymity must be strictly preserved. You will often need to reassure interviewees of our commitment to confidentiality. The identity of respondents must not be disclosed to any third party. No personal data should be shared with anyone outside TREPA unless specifically authorized by the principal researcher."

IX. Informed Consent

Researchers then discussed the informed consent process with the data enumerators, following the script provided below:

"All interviews conducted by TREPA are VOLUNTARY. Although TREPA makes every effort to make sure that we attain the highest possible hit rates, participants are not obliged to

participate in our data collection activities nor to answer all questions. No interview can take place without the consent of the respondent. You should not coerce respondents, threaten them, or offer any inducement. In most cases, the interviewee will be required to verbally provide his/her consent and where possible, they will be required to sign a consent form. You must explain what the consent means. It is important for the participant to freely agree to the consent before starting the interview. You should never promise services or rewards for responding to questions or give the impression that services will improve because of the interviews, data collection, or research activities.”

X. Non-Disclosure Agreement

Researchers continued explaining the non-disclosure agreement by following the script below:

“A key element in preserving confidentiality is to have all individuals involved in field activities (data collection or conducting interviews) sign a non-disclosure agreement (NDA) before commencing their employment.

The non-disclosure agreement prevents you from:

- a) Discussing responses with colleagues unless expressly authorized by the TREPA’s supervisor.*
- b) Discussing the responses with any intentions of malice.*
- c) Discussing the responses with non-TREPA team members.*
- d) Revealing the identity of any participants to others.*
- e) Sharing any details of the data collection activities with people outside of the TREPA team.*

By adhering to these guidelines, we ensure the integrity and confidentiality of our research process.”

XI. Interview Techniques

At this point, researchers explained interview techniques, by following the guidelines provided below:

“During the interview, allow respondents to take their time without suggesting answers. Work steadily and ensure that their answers are clear to you before recording them. If you believe a statement is mistaken, tactfully ask further questions to obtain accurate answers.

In some cases, individuals may refuse to be interviewed, often due to misunderstandings. Remain courteous and emphasize the importance of the interview, clarifying that it is unrelated to law enforcement or government activities. Explain that the information is used solely for research purposes, that no identifiable data will be retained, and that the results will be published as data tables and summaries, ensuring the anonymity of individual respondents.

If you cannot resolve misunderstandings or if a refusal is deliberate, reassure the individual that it is acceptable to withdraw from the interview or skip specific questions. Continue with the data collection, making a note of any unanswered questions. Share this information with the TREPA team as soon as possible.”

XII. Basic Principles for Completing Questionnaires

Data enumerators were then trained on how to complete a questionnaire by following the script below:

“There are some basic principles that you should observe in completing the questionnaire.

- a) Always read the questions exactly as they are written in the questionnaire (Portuguese or Shangaan). After reading a question once in a clear and comprehensible manner, you should await the reply. If the respondent does not answer in a reasonable time, he has probably (i) not heard the question; (ii) not understood the question, or (iii) does not know the answer. In any case, if there is no answer, repeat the question. If there*

- is still no reply, you must ask whether the question has been understood. If the answer is 'No', you may reword the question. If the difficulty lies in finding the right answer, you should encourage the respondent to reply by stating if he/she can explain in a few words what he/she thinks. Then, record their answer. If they insist on not replying, reassure them this is okay, and pass to the next question.*
- b) Completeness of questionnaire: After finishing each interview, verify that all the sections of the questionnaire have been correctly completed. Check to see that your writing can be easily read. Be sure you have recorded the required information for all of the participants indicated in each section. You should review your questionnaires immediately after each interview before you hand over the questionnaire to your supervisor.*
 - c) You can correct minor errors on the interview forms, like sloppy writing or light entries. However, you should not make any other changes in the completed questionnaire without asking the respondent the questions again. Also, you may not copy the information you have collected onto a new questionnaire.*
 - d) Fill out the questionnaire with a **blue pen ONLY**. There will be no exceptions.*
 - e) If you make an error, put a single line across the incorrect answer and record the correct answer beside it.*

XIII. Administering Questionnaires

Researchers continued the training by providing further information pursuant to the script below:

“When meeting new research participants, begin by exchanging greetings and introducing yourself. During this introduction period, be sure to cover the following points:

- a) **Explain the Purpose:** Clearly explain the purpose of the interview. If needed, use the introduction letters provided by TREPA, if any;
- b) **Topic Explanation:** Inform the participant that many of the questions will be about animals, the environment, and humans. Ask if they are knowledgeable about these issues and if they are willing to speak with you;
- c) **Interview Duration:** If the person agrees to be interviewed, inform them that the interview will take approximately 30-60 minutes;
- d) **Consent:** Ensure the respondent provides verbal consent and/or signs the Consent Form, where applicable;
- e) **Privacy:** Ensure the interview is private. Make sure no one else is present or within hearing range during the interview;
- f) **Questions:** Ask the interviewee if they have any other questions or need any clarification before starting the interview;
- g) **Start the Interview:** Start the interview and interview the interviewee using the interview protocol;
- h) **Interview wrap-up:** Ask the interviewee if they have any questions for you or any additional information they would like to provide, and address each accordingly;
- i) **Closing:** If they do not have any additional information and questions for you, thank them for their time and the opportunity to speak with them, then proceed with closing the interview.

By following these steps, you will create a respectful and professional environment for conducting the interview from start to finish.”

XIV. Debriefing Session

Data enumerators were informed that after they finished conducting their surveys, they were required to meet with the TREPA team members for a feedback session where the activities of the day were discussed and evaluated, and suggestions and recommendations for improvements were advanced.